

**STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF UNITS REPRESENTING THE CONCEPT
OF "DEATH"**

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Abstract: In this scientific article, we have explained the statistical analysis of phraseological units expressing the concept of "Death" in English and Uzbek languages. It can be seen that the examples in English and Uzbek languages are clearly proven.

Key words: Euphemism and phraseological units in English and Uzbek, statistical analysis, morphological analysis.

**СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЕДИНИЦ, ПРЕДСТАВЛЯЮЩИХ
ПОНЯТИЕ «СМЕРТЬ»**

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье мы разъяснили статистический анализ фразеологизмов, выражающих концепт «Смерть» в английском и узбекском языках. Видно, что примеры на английском и узбекском языках наглядно доказаны.

Ключевые слова: Эвфемизмы и фразеологические единицы английского и узбекского языков, статистический анализ, морфологический анализ.

In recent years, due to the growing intercultural relations, linguists pay great attention to the study of the cultures of different peoples, their peculiarities, used gestures, customs and manners. Every person in the society, while communicating with another representative of speech, certainly uses the national customs and expressions of his people and reflects them in his speech. In Uzbek culture, it is a long-standing tradition to speak softly so as not to offend the interlocutor. One of the language units close to this is euphemisms, which mean "soft expression" in Greek, and are synonyms that appeared to soften harsher words and phrases that are uncomfortable to say. One of the main tasks of euphemism is to avoid telling the listener a negative reality, it is used in order to protect it from its negative and inappropriate complications. In this case, bad and cold messages are blocked and delivered to the speaker in a soft form instead. For example: instead of saying "died", using euphemisms such as "passed away, passed away, handed over his deposit" serves to protect the human mind from negative influences. The famous linguist B.A. Larin of XX-XXI centuries defines euphemisms as follows: "Euphemisms are temporary. A speech situation is necessary for its use, that is, there must be equivalents of rude words. If words that are difficult to use are excluded from communication, euphemisms lose their value and become ordinary lexemes.

The scientist divides euphemisms into 3 groups:

1. Miliy - common euphemisms of the literary language.
2. Class and professional euphemisms.
3. Household euphemisms.

In 1964, Uzbek linguist Ne'mat Ismatullayev defended his thesis on "Euphemisms of the modern Uzbek literary language" and thematically divided Uzbek euphemisms into 3 types:

1. Euphemisms used instead of names of poisonous insects.
2. Softening euphemisms used for the elderly.
3. Wife - euphemisms used in the language of girls.

Similar to these views, other linguists have given opinions on euphemisms along the way. Among them, H.Shamsiddinov expressed his views on synonymous functional-semantic euphemisms of words, while A.E.Mamatov focused on the euphemism and dysphemism formation of phraseology.

For example, there are euphemisms for "death" in English, which are described as follows.

Dead, die. death - (dead) instead of harsh words, passed on, lose one's life, meet one's end, peg out, to be done, lose your life, depart, expire, kick the bucket, Words like meet your maker(God), pop off are used. **In the Uzbek language**, it is customary to describe the death of a person with euphemisms, that is, with words that do not touch the heart and do not sink in: He died - his rude, cold words were replaced, he handed over his deposit, he went to God, his soul was cut off, he was a servant, be patient, he died, he passed away, he is no longer among us. , the day is over, the day is over, the doomsday is over, and the words are widely used. Our research shows that there are 10 euphemisms used to soften the word "death" in English, and 13 in Uzbek.

Statistical analysis of units representing the concept of "death".

Table 1

N%	Units representing "Death" total	Uzbek language	English language	Total
1	Phraseological units	29	88	117
2	Euphemisms	13	10	23

In addition, we can find folk proverbs in the Uzbek language, even in the English culture, that embody the meaning and meaning of "death", which has been known

and famous since time immemorial. Now we will look at the proverbs that mean "death" in the cultures of both languages and analyze them.

Proverbs are another type of folklore that has been passed down from our ancestors to us, reflecting the national culture and traditions of the people. Proverbs are preserved in concise and simple forms and are highly respected by linguists as a resource that invites people to education and guides them to understand right and wrong. In English-speaking countries, there are also proverbs that reflect their national culture and express "death".

"When death is there it is over". (There is death everywhere) Russian proverb.

"When death comes, the rich man has no money and the poor has no debt." (When death comes, the rich have no money and the poor have no debt, everyone is equal) Jewish proverb.

"When an old man marries, death laughs". (When an old man marries, death laughs) German proverb.

"What is sport to the cat is death to the mouse." (A mouse that sees a cat must die) is a German proverb.

"We come and cry and that is

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